

**THE FABRICATION AND PROPERTIES OF
ALUMINA-DUCTILE METAL PARTICLE COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

Three composites based on an alumina matrix and containing 20 volume per cent of ductile metal (nickel or iron) particles have been fabricated by hot pressing powder blends. Both indentation and double torsion testing have indicated that all of the composites are tougher than the parent matrix, with increases ranging from 22 to 78%. Although indentation testing gives an indication of relative performance, problems with using this method have been outlined. Results from the double torsion tests, on alumina-iron specimens from different processing routes, have shown the importance of microstructure. It was also noted that the maximum toughness in each composite was only achieved at relatively long crack lengths (of the order of millimetres). Examination of crack profiles suggests that the particle-matrix interface is weak and an improvement in the interfacial strength would increase the toughness of the composites further.

KEYWORDS: Ceramic matrix composite; particulate composite; toughening; brittle matrix; ductile particle.

1. INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of ceramic particles or whiskers in ceramic matrices is well established as a method of increasing toughness. However, the toughening increments that can be achieved are modest and typically the toughness of the parent matrix material is doubled. Fibre composites offer potentially larger increases but have an associated loss of isotropy. The inclusion of ductile particles, capable of plastically deforming and bridging crack faces, is an alternative approach to producing materials that are tougher than conventional particulate second phase materials (e.g. SiC-TiB₂) yet are still isotropic.

In systems containing a ductile second phase the majority of the toughening increase is believed to be a result of the plastic deformation of the metallic inclusions spanning the faces of the growing crack [1, 2, 3]. The toughening increment can be estimated from the work of rupture of the ductile phase, which is given by the product of the nominal stress (σ) and the displacement (u) of the unconstrained particle. Thus,

$$\Delta G = A_f \int_0^{u^*} \sigma(u) du \quad (1)$$

where A_f is the area fraction of the second phase and u^* is the crack opening displacement upon rupture of the ductile ligament. Scaling the nominal stress with the yield stress (σ_y) and u with a characteristic dimension of the second phase (r) gives

$$\Delta G = CA_f \sigma_y r \quad (2)$$

where C is a constant known as the constraint factor. This accounts for the difference in deformation behaviour between constrained and unconstrained particles [3]. ΔG and E , the Young's modulus, can then be used to calculate ΔK , the increase in fracture toughness.

There have been several studies of properties of brittle matrices containing ductile second phases [e.g. 4, 5, 6] but the two most relevant to the present work are those by Flinn et al [3] and Tuan and Brook [7]. Both sets of workers investigated composites based on an alumina matrix: alumina-aluminium fabricated via the LanxideTM process in the case of Flinn and co-workers, alumina-nickel formed by in situ reduction of nickel oxide in alumina in the case of Tuan and Brook.

This study is concerned with nickel and iron particles in alumina. Although these metals have favourable ductility and refractory characteristics, they were chosen primarily because they react with alumina to metal aluminates (spinel). Thus, it is anticipated that the interfacial bond strength between the particle and the matrix can be manipulated through the control of the extent of reaction.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Composite Fabrication Composite powders were prepared by dry milling alumina powder (AKP-30, Sumitomo Chemical Co. Ltd. Tokyo, Japan) and metal powder (nickel supplied by Goodfellow Advanced Materials, Cambridge, U K or iron supplied by H.C. Starck, Dusseldorf, Germany). The proportions of alumina and metal were calculated to give 20 vol% metal in the final product (taking the theoretical densities as 3980 kg m⁻³ for alumina, 8880 kg m⁻³ for nickel and 7860 kg m⁻³ for iron). Three types of starting powder were produced: alumina-nickel (as milled), alumina-iron (as milled) and alumina-iron (sieved after milling).

Dense composite specimens were fabricated by hot pressing in a graphite die heated by a graphite element, both of which were prevented from oxidation by an argon atmosphere. In order to compare the properties of the composite with the parent matrix, a small amount of alumina was pressed concomitantly with the composite. Pressing schedules are given in Table 1.

Table 1 : Summary of Pressing Schedules

Specimen	Holding Temp./°C	Pressure/MPa	Time/min
Al ₂ O ₃ -Ni	1400	30	30
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (sieved)	1350	25	30
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (unsieved)	1350	25	30

2.2 Microstructural Characterisation The densities of the composites were determined by Archimedes' principle. Specimens were lightly abraded to remove the sinter skin prior to immersion in water. X-ray diffractometry (XRD), reflected light microscopy (RLM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were performed on samples of composite cut from pressed billets and polished to a 1µm diamond surface finish using conventional metallographic preparation techniques.

2.3 Determination of Indentation Fracture Toughness Polished samples of all the composites were indented by a Vickers profile diamond. Where possible, fracture toughness values were calculated from the length of radial cracks surrounding 20 and 30 kg indentations, using the universal formula of Liang et al [8]. Results were averaged over at least ten indentations per sample. Indentation crack profiles were examined in the SEM.

2.4 Determination of Fracture Toughness by Double Torsion Testing The double torsion specimen geometry and testing arrangement is shown in Figure 1. Specimens dimensions were approximately l=22 mm, t=2 mm, t_n=0.35 mm. The samples were tested in the chamber of a Cambridge Instruments Stereoscan S100, allowing in situ observation of crack growth. Loading, to a maximum of P=370 N, was as shown in Figure 1 with W=9.5 mm and W_m=2 mm.

The fracture toughness, K_I , was calculated using the formula

$$K_I = PW_m \left(\frac{3}{Wt^3 \tau_n (1 - \nu) \xi} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

where ξ is given by

$$\xi = 1 - 0.6302 \tau + 1.20 \tau \exp \left(\frac{-\pi}{\tau} \right) \quad (4)$$

and $\tau = 2t/W$. ν is Poisson's ratio (taken as 0.3).

Figure 1 : Schematic of the double torsion specimen geometry and loading configuration.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructural Characterisation

The densities and microstructural characteristics of the composite materials are given in Table 2. From the density measurements, it can be seen that the fabrication procedure produces dense composites which contain alumina and the metal as the major phases. The possibility of the formation of trace amounts of nickel or iron aluminate cannot be discounted. It should be noted that the alumina-nickel material has been the subject of a wider study and thus, the processing route for this material is closer to optimum than for the alumina-iron system.

Table 2 : Microstructural Characteristics of the Three Composites

Specimen	Density/% theoretical	XRD observations	Vol % metal
Al ₂ O ₃ -Ni	99.6	α -Al ₂ O ₃ and Ni	20
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (sieved)	96.9	α -Al ₂ O ₃ and α -Fe	20
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (unsieved)	96.9	α -Al ₂ O ₃ and α -Fe	20

Figure 2 shows micrographs of typical microstructures of the two alumina-iron composites. The microstructure of the alumina-nickel material is very similar to that of the composite made from sieved powder. The porosity is attributed to grain pull-out during specimen preparation. The alumina-nickel composite and the material prepared from sieved alumina-iron powder show homogeneous distributions of the metallic phase. It is clear that the exclusion of the sieving step produces an aggregation of alumina particles in the alumina-iron system but not the alumina-nickel system. In the unsieved alumina-iron material the iron particles are closer together than in the sieved, but the particle size is approximately the same in the two materials.

Figure 2 : Reflected light micrographs of the alumina-iron composites made from (a) milled and sieved powder and (b) as-milled powder.

Figure 3 : A 20 kg indentation in the alumina-nickel composite.

3.2 Indentation Fracture Toughness The length of the radial cracks emanating from the corners of indentations, such as the one shown in Figure 3, have been used to calculate a fracture toughness value. The results of the indentation tests are given in Table 3. These suggest that all of the composites are tougher than the parent matrix, with the alumina-iron materials being tougher than the alumina-nickel. However, there are clearly problems associated with obtaining a value for the fracture toughness from this type of test. Indentations in the two alumina-iron composites produced no reproducible radial cracks (although there was evidence of lateral cracking) and a wide range of responses to indentation were observed. The alumina-nickel material did exhibit radial cracking but Figure 3 shows that some regions of the indentation have deformed or cracked in an unusual manner, thus consuming energy and leaving less available for the formation of radial cracks. This results in an over-estimation of the fracture toughness of this material, but probably not of the alumina which shows only the characteristic crack patterns. This over-estimation might in part be countered if the material shows R-curve behaviour; if the cracks are relatively short, i.e. shorter than the length of the fully developed process zone, the plateau value of K_c will not be reached and the toughness will be under-estimated. Although the indentation method does not appear to be suitable for the determination of fracture toughness in these materials, the lack of cracking in the alumina-iron composites may be an indication of a high resistance to wear by hard, sharp particles.

Table 3 : Indentation Toughness Values

Specimen	Mean K_c (ind)/MPa m ^{1/2}	Range of K_c (ind)/MPa m ^{1/2}
Alumina	4.2	4.1 - 4.3
Al ₂ O ₃ -Ni	10.6	7.5 - 13.7
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (sieved)	lack of radial crack formation suggests that these materials are tougher than the other two, but it is not possible to obtain an indentation fracture toughness value.	
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (unsieved)		

Table 4 : Results of the Double Torsion Tests

Specimen	Initial K_{Ic} /MPa m ^{1/2}	Plateau K_{Ic} /MPa m ^{1/2}	ΔK /MPa m ^{1/2} (%increase)	Proc. zone length/mm
Al ₂ O ₃ -Ni	3.7	5.6	1.9 (51)	1.1
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (sieved)	4.1	5.0	0.9 (22)	0.7
Al ₂ O ₃ -Fe (unsieved)	4.1	7.3	3.2 (78)	3.3

3.3 Double Torsion Testing The results of the double torsion experiments are summarised in Table 4. Whilst all of the composite materials toughness values are higher than those of the parent matrix, they are not as high as would be expected from the indentation behaviour. However, the initial K_{Ic} values are representative of the fracture toughness of the parent matrix; these are in good agreement with the value obtained by indentation, suggesting that this method is suitable for the assessment of fracture toughness in materials which develop the classical crack patterns. It is unfortunate that indentation behaviour can only be used as a very rough guide to toughness in the composite systems since it is very quick and convenient compared to other fracture toughness tests.

Comparing the alumina-nickel and alumina-iron (sieved) results it can be seen that the alumina-nickel material is the tougher. This is contrary to the results of indentation testing but as expected from consideration of equation 2. The microstructural characteristics of the two materials are very similar. If they were identical in every respect apart from the nature of the metal, then the particulate phase with the higher yield stress would produce the tougher composite. Although we cannot be sure of the precise yield stress of the particles used in these composites it is not unreasonable to expect the nickel to have a higher value than the iron.

Figure 4 shows a crack in the alumina-nickel composite. It is clear that the matrix-particle interface is weak and a preferred fracture path. There is very little evidence of ligament stretching in this composite or the less tough of the two alumina-iron composites. The increase in toughness is probably a combination of energy absorption by crack deflection and friction as the particles are pulled out of their sockets when the crack faces separate. Figure 5 shows a nickel particle and, on the opposite fracture surface, the hole from which it has been extracted. It can be seen that the particle surface is rough and would give rise to frictional effects. However, the particle shows no evidence of plastic deformation and hence, the fracture toughness value is relatively low.

Figure 4 : SEM photomicrograph of a crack in a double torsion test specimen of alumina-nickel.

Figure 5 : SEM photomicrographs of details of two opposing fracture surfaces in alumina-nickel showing (a) a hole and (b) the nickel particle that has been pulled from it.

Figure 6 : SEM photomicrograph of a crack interacting with, and causing plastic deformation of, an iron particle in the toughest of the composites.

The difference in measured fracture toughness values between the two alumina-iron composites highlights the effect that processing can have on properties. These two materials differ only in one processing step. The larger scale inhomogeneities of the composite made from the unsieved powder mean that the crack has to take a more tortuous path to avoid the particles. Thus, the weak matrix-particle interface is less of a problem in this material compared to the other alumina-iron composite. Figure 6 shows the crack in a double torsion experiment interacting with an iron particle. It is clear the particle is undergoing plastic deformation and this will lead to higher toughness values than those due to crack deflection.

In order to increase the toughness of these composites further it is necessary to improve the particle-matrix bond strength so that the crack does not have the option of an easy fracture path and instead has to interact with the metal particles. Future work will investigate modifications to the processing route which will increase the oxygen content of the sample and increase the likelihood of metal aluminate formation at the interface. This could be achieved most easily by heat treating the nickel powder in air to encourage the formation of a thicker skin of nickel oxide.

It should be noted that all of the composites show R-curve behaviour i.e. the toughness increases until a steady state process zone has been established. The tougher materials have longer process zones. This may be a problem in the use of these materials.

The results from the present study compare favourably with those from other workers. Extrapolation of the results of Tuan and Brook [7] to a metal content of 20 vol% suggests a composite with a indentation fracture toughness of $5.8 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ compared to a matrix value of $2.75 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$. The corresponding ΔG value is 65 J m^{-2} . The increase in indentation fracture toughness for the alumina-nickel composite in the present study corresponds to a ΔG value of about 240 J m^{-2} . However, the average particle size of the particles in the Tuan and Brook study is $2 \mu\text{m}$ compared to $6 \mu\text{m}$ in this work. Thus, according to equation 2, the value of 65 J m^{-2} should be multiplied by a factor of three to give a fair comparison. This gives results which are in close agreement. Likewise, the toughening increment is estimated to be about 120 J m^{-2} for the toughener of the two alumina-iron materials, tested in double torsion. Values of $150\text{-}200 \text{ J m}^{-2}$ were measured for the alumina-aluminium chevron notched specimens investigated by Flinn et al [3].

4. CONCLUSIONS

Three alumina-metal composites have been fabricated and all of them are tougher than the parent matrix. The toughest composite is an alumina-iron material in which the iron particles are unevenly distributed giving rise to a tortuous crack path and plastic deformation of the metallic particles. In the other two materials, which contain homogeneous distributions of iron and nickel particles, the crack is able to by-pass the particles and follow weak particle-matrix interfaces. Double torsion testing inside an SEM has been shown to be a suitable method for measuring fracture toughness and observing crack growth in these materials. Problems with the simpler technique of indentation testing have been outlined. However, the lack of indentation cracking in these materials may indicate their suitability for resisting wear by hard, sharp particles.

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